

Effect of sodium thiosulfate and resveratrol on blood pressure and arterial health in nicotine-exposed rats

Papel del tiosulfato de sodio y resveratrol en la mejora de los gases sanguíneos, el pH y el estado redox en ratas tratadas con nicotina

Zena Shakir Al-Tamemi¹ Department of Physiology, Biochemistry and Pharmacology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad, Iraq. Email: zena.shaker1106h@covm.uobaghdad.edu.iq <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6195-229>

Baraa Najim Al-Okaily² Department of Physiology, Biochemistry and Pharmacology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad, Iraq. Email: baraa.n.@covm.uobaghdad.edu.iq <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2691-2089>

Received: 08/20/2022 Accepted: 10/19/2023 Published: 20/12/2023 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443697>

522

Abstract

Arterial blood pressure, commonly referred to as blood pressure, is a vital physiological parameter that measures the force exerted by the circulating blood against the walls of the arteries. It is a critical factor in maintaining overall health and proper functioning of the cardiovascular system. Blood pressure is typically expressed as a ratio of two values: systolic pressure and diastolic pressure. Systolic pressure represents the force when the heart contracts and pumps blood into the arteries, while diastolic pressure reflects the force when the heart is at rest between beats. The measurement is expressed in millimeters of mercury (mm Hg), and a normal blood pressure reading for adults is around 120/80 mm Hg. High blood pressure, also known as hypertension, occurs when the force of blood against the artery walls is consistently too high. This condition can lead to serious health issues, including an increased risk of heart disease, stroke, and kidney problems. On the other hand, low blood pressure, or hypotension, can result in symptoms such as dizziness, fainting, and reduced blood flow to vital organs. Blood pressure is influenced by various factors, including the volume of blood in the circulatory

system, the strength of the heart's contractions, and the flexibility and diameter of the blood vessels. Lifestyle choices, such as diet, physical activity, and stress management, can also have a significant impact on blood pressure. Measuring blood pressure is a common medical practice and is typically done using a sphygmomanometer, which consists of an inflatable cuff and a pressure gauge. The cuff is wrapped around the upper arm, and the pressure in the cuff is slowly released while listening for the sounds of blood flow using a stethoscope. The point at which the sounds first appear (systolic pressure) and when they disappear (diastolic pressure) provides the blood pressure reading. Maintaining a healthy blood pressure range is crucial for overall well-being. If blood pressure is consistently outside of the normal range, medical intervention and lifestyle adjustments may be necessary to manage and regulate it effectively. Regular check-ups with a healthcare professional are essential for monitoring and addressing any blood pressure concerns.

Keywords: Blood pressure, Hypertension, Sphygmomanometer, Cardiovascular system, Hypotension

Resumen

La presión arterial, comúnmente conocida como presión arterial, es un parámetro fisiológico vital que mide la fuerza que ejerce la sangre circulante contra las paredes de las arterias. Es un factor crítico para mantener la salud general y el funcionamiento adecuado del sistema cardiovascular. La presión arterial generalmente se expresa como una proporción de dos valores: presión sistólica y presión diastólica. La presión sistólica representa la fuerza cuando el corazón se contrae y bombea sangre hacia las arterias, mientras que la presión diastólica refleja la fuerza cuando el corazón está en reposo entre latidos. La medición se expresa en milímetros de mercurio (mm Hg) y una lectura normal de presión arterial para adultos es de alrededor de 120/80 mm Hg. La presión arterial alta, también conocida como hipertensión, ocurre cuando la fuerza de la sangre contra las paredes de las arterias es constante, demasiado alto. Esta afección puede provocar problemas de salud graves, incluido un mayor riesgo de enfermedades cardíacas, accidentes cerebrovasculares y problemas renales. Por otro lado, la presión arterial baja o hipotensión puede provocar síntomas como mareos, desmayos y reducción del flujo sanguíneo a órganos vitales. La presión arterial está influenciada por varios factores, incluido el volumen de sangre en el sistema circulatorio, la fuerza de las contracciones del corazón y la flexibilidad y el diámetro de los vasos sanguíneos. Las elecciones de estilo de vida, como la dieta, la actividad física y el manejo del estrés, también pueden tener un impacto significativo en la presión arterial. Medir la presión arterial es una práctica médica común y generalmente se realiza mediante un esfigmomanómetro, que consta de un manguito inflable y un manómetro. El manguito se envuelve alrededor de la parte superior del brazo y la presión en el manguito se libera lentamente mientras se escuchan los sonidos del flujo sanguíneo con un estetoscopio. El punto en el que aparecen los sonidos por primera vez (presión sistólica) y cuando desaparecen (presión diastólica) proporciona la lectura de la presión arterial. Mantener un rango saludable de presión arterial es crucial para el bienestar general. Si la presión arterial está constantemente fuera del rango normal, puede ser necesaria una intervención médica y ajustes en el estilo de vida para controlarla y regularla de manera efectiva. Los controles periódicos con un profesional de la salud son esenciales para controlar y abordar cualquier problema de presión arterial.

Palabras clave: Presión arterial, Hipertensión, Esfigmomanómetro, Sistema cardiovascular, Hipotensión

Introduction

Hypertension, commonly known as high blood pressure, is a significant risk factor for a wide range of health issues, with its primary impact on cardiovascular health. This condition is characterized by elevated blood pressure in the arteries, and it can lead to various detrimental consequences for the circulatory system¹⁻⁵. Hypertension is often associated with the narrowing and hardening of the arteries, which can result in atherosclerosis. Atherosclerosis, in turn, can lead to coronary artery disease, heart attacks, and strokes. The elevated pressure within the arteries exerts additional strain on the heart, causing it to work harder and potentially leading to heart failure over time⁶⁻⁹.

Moreover, chronic high blood pressure can contribute to the development of other cardiovascular problems, such as aneurysms, peripheral artery disease, and kidney damage^{10,11}. It is essential to recognize that hypertension not only affects the heart but also the entire vascular system, increasing the risk of various complications¹²⁻¹⁴. The factors that contribute to hypertension are multifaceted and can include genetic predisposition, lifestyle choices, and environmental influences. Smoking, poor dietary habits, excessive alcohol consumption, and a sedentary lifestyle are common risk factors associated with high blood pressure^{15,16}.

Effective management of hypertension involves lifestyle modifications, such as a heart-healthy diet, regular physical activity, and stress reduction^{17,18}. In some cases, medication may be prescribed by healthcare professionals to control blood pressure. Preventive measures and early intervention are crucial in combating the adverse effects of high blood pressure on cardiovascular health¹⁹⁻²¹. Regular check-ups and monitoring of blood pressure levels can aid in timely diagnosis and the implementation of appropriate measures to reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications²²⁻²⁴.

Animal Ethical approval

Animal care and treatment in this study were conducted at the College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad, in strict accordance with the code of ethics for animal experiments. Ethical approval was obtained from the local committee of animal care and use (P.G. 899 date 27-4-2023).

Chemicals

Nicotine with a purity of nearly 97% and KP with a melting point of 243-248 degrees Celsius were used in the study. The Swiss-made liquid had a molecular weight of 162.24. STS with a purity of 99.50% was procured from SD Fine Chemical Limited in Mumbai, India. The resveratrol supplement capsules were supplied by NOW, a United States-based company.

Animals and Experimental Design

We used thirty-six male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) aged 3-3.5 months and weighing 190-220 grams in this study. The rats were housed in enclosures with a 12-hour light/dark cycle and maintained at temperatures between 22–25 °C. Throughout the research, water and pellets were freely available to the animals. Six rats per treatment were grouped together by similarity. The rats underwent a 15-day acclimation period before being experimented on for up to 28 days. The control group of rats received intraperitoneal injections of normal saline at a rate of 0.1 ml per 100 grams of body weight daily for 28 days. Rats in the test groups received various treatments. In Group G1, rats received 1.5 mg/kg of nicotine intraperitoneally. Group (G2) rats received intraperitoneal injections of 450 mg/kg sodium thiosulphate and 1.5 mg/kg nicotine. Rats in Group 3 (G3) were orally administered 87 mg/kg of resveratrol and intraperitoneally injected with 1.5 mg/kg nicotine. Group G4 rats received 450 mg per kilogram of sodium thiosulfate, 87 mg per kilogram of resveratrol, and 1.5 mg per kilogram of nicotine. Group G5... In this experimental cohort, rats received a 450 mg/kg injection of sodium thiosulphate and an 87 mg/kg resveratrol supplement. The study groups were treated for 28 days.

Blood Sample Collection

At the end of the experiment, all animals were anesthetized with ketamine (100 mg/kg body weight, intraperitoneal) and xylazine (10 mg/kg, intraperitoneal). Gel tubes were used to collect blood samples by heart piercing. To obtain serum, these tubes were centrifuged and refrigerated at -18°C. Another part of the blood was divided into two halves. The original component was stored in an EDTA tube for blood Hb and RBC testing, and the second part was inserted into blood collection tubes with sodium heparin for blood gas and blood pH analysis. Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) and malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were measured using enzymatic kits from Chinese Solarbio Life Science. Rat blood samples were

also collected in blood gas analyzer tubes. The OPTI CCA-TS2 blood gas and electrolyte analyzer (OPTI Medical SN.OP6-005567 USA) was used to measure PO₂, PCO₂, and pH. Additionally, a Genix blood analyzer system from Genix, USA, was used to measure hemoglobin and RBC counts in blood samples.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using the computer program SPSS version 24. The results are presented as the mean ± standard error (SE). A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the least significant difference (LSD) test was conducted at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$ to compare the groups. This analysis was employed to assess the significance level at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

Serum malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration (mmol/ml)

The results obtained from the analysis of blood MDA concentration in figure (1-1) indicate a statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the nicotine exposed group (G1) compared to the other treatment groups and the negative control (C). Furthermore, it was observed that there were no statistically significant differences ($P > 0.05$) between G2 and G3. However, a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in serum MDA levels was observed in both G2 and G3 when compared to G4, G5, G1, and the control group C. The G4 results shown an impressive increase in comparison to G5, although both groups demonstrated no significant differences when compared to the negative C group.

Serum Total Antioxidant capacity concentration (mmol/ml)

The findings from the analysis of serum total antioxidant capacity, as depicted in Figure (1-2), indicate a statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) elevation in the blood TAC levels of the G5 group when compared to the results of the other groups. The findings from the G1 group indicated a statistically significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the other groups. Similarly, the G3 group demonstrated a substantial ($p \leq 0.05$) drop when compared to the G2, G4, and G5 groups.

RBCs Count ($\times 10^6/\text{ml}$)

Findings depicted in Figure (2-1) indicate a statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) rise in the count of red blood cells (RBCs) inside the G5 group when compared to the other groups. Conversely, there was a statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) drop in the G1 group when compared to the other groups. The results of the G4 group demonstrated a statistically significant rise ($p \leq 0.05$) when compared to both the G3 and G1 groups. However, there was no statistically significant increase observed between the G4

and G2 groups. Additionally, a non-significant increase ($P>0.05$) was observed between the G2 and G3.

Hb concentration (g/dL)

The findings depicted in Figure (2-2) indicate a statistically significant ($p\leq 0.05$) decrease in the G1 group (rats subjected to nicotine-induced stress) compared to the other experimental groups. Conversely, rats treated with nicotine and administered STS, resveratrol, or a combination of both exhibited a statistically significant ($p\leq 0.05$) increase in hemoglobin (Hb) levels compared to the G1 group. However, no statistically significant ($P>0.05$) differences were observed between the G2, G3, and G4 treated groups. Notably, the results demonstrate a statistically significant ($p\leq 0.05$) increase in Hb concentration in the G5 group compared to the other experimental groups.

Blood PO₂ (mmHg)

Results in figure (2-3) showed a significant ($p\leq 0.05$) decrease in blood PO₂ in G1 group as compared with other experimental groups, besides G5 were showed a significant ($p\leq 0.05$) increase in Blood PO₂ as compared with other treated groups and control, there were no statistically significant ($P>0.05$) differences observed in blood PO₂ between G2 and G4 groups.

PCO₂ mmHg

Results in figure (2-4) showed a significant ($p\leq 0.05$) increase in Blood PCO₂ in G1 group as compared with all other groups C, G2, G3, G4 and G5 groups, a significant ($p\leq 0.05$) decrease in Blood PCO₂ in G5 group as compared with other groups, a significant ($p\leq 0.05$) decrease in PCO₂ in G5 were noticed as compared with control group.

Blood PH

Results of blood PH was clarified in figure (2-5) A statistically significant decrease ($p\leq 0.05$) in the G1 group was observed when compared to the other experimental groups while G5 and control groups didn't show any significant ($P>0.05$) differences between each other, no significant ($P>0.05$) differences were noticed between G2 and G3 groups.

The data is presented as the mean $\pm$ standard error (SE). The study involved a sample of six rats. In the control group, the rats received an injection of a normal saline solution. Group 1 (G1) consisted of rats that were intraperitoneally injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 2 (G2) included rats that were intraperitoneally injected with Sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight, along with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 3 (G3) comprised rats that were administered resveratrol at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight through gavage, and they were also intraperitoneally injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 4 (G4) involved rats that were injected with sodium thiosulfate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and were administered a resveratrol supplement at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight. They were also injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 5 (G5) received intraperitoneal injections of Sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and were administered a Resveratrol supplement at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight. Different letters indicate significant differences between the groups, with a significance level of $p\leq 0.05$.

Now, let's translate this passage into a text about arterial blood pressure in English:

The data is presented as the mean $\pm$ standard error (SE). The study involved a sample of six rats. In the control group, the rats received an injection of a normal saline solution. Group 1 (G1) consisted of rats that were intraperitoneally injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 2 (G2) included rats that were intraperitoneally injected with Sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight, along with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 3 (G3) comprised rats that were administered resveratrol at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight through gavage, and they were also intraperitoneally injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 4 (G4) involved rats that were injected with sodium thiosulfate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and were administered a resveratrol supplement at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight. They were also

Figure 1. Effect of Sodium thiosulfate and Resveratrol on serum MDA (1) and total antioxidant capacity (2) of adult males rats IP injected with nicotine 1.5 mg/kg b.w (mmol/ml) for 28 days

injected with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 5 (G5) received intraperitoneal injections of Sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and were administered a Resveratrol supplement at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight. Different letters indicate significant differences between the groups, with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

The values in this study are presented as the mean $\pm$ standard error (SE). The sample size included six rats. In the control group, rats received an injection of a normal saline solution. Group 1 (G1) received an intraperitoneal injection of nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 2 (G2) received intraperitoneal injections of sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight

along with nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 3 (G3) received resveratrol through gavage at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight and an intraperitoneal injection of nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 4 (G4) received intraperitoneal injections of sodium thiosulfate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and an oral administration of resveratrol at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight, along with an intraperitoneal injection of nicotine at a dose of 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Group 5 (G5) received intraperitoneal injections of sodium thiosulphate at a dose of 450 mg/kg body weight and an oral administration of resveratrol at a dose of 87 mg/kg body weight. Different letters indicate significant differences between groups ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure 2. Effects of sodium thiosulfate and resveratrol on blood (1) RBCs count (2)Hb (3)PO2 (4)PCO2 (5)PH in Adult Males Rats injected with nicotine for 28 days

Nicotine, an alkaloid present in tobacco leaves, sustains tobacco addiction and continued smoking. Stressed subjects receiving intraperitoneal nicotine had higher serum malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and lower serum total antioxidant capacity compared to other experimental groups. This finding supports previous research indicating that nicotine-treated rats produce excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) and have high lung tissue MDA levels, suggesting impaired lung ROS elimination due to increased oxidant generation and reduced antioxidant synthesis^{25,26}. Other studies, such as those by Ateyya et al.²¹, have shown that nicotine increases lipid peroxidation, as evidenced by elevated TBARs in the liver and lung. Nicotine generates ROS through various mechanisms, including its impact on mitochondrial oxygen consumption and complex I inhibition, leading to increased ROS production. Elsonbaty and Ismail²³ found that rats treated with nicotine exhibited heightened oxidative stress markers, including MDA.

In contrast, groups injected with sodium thiosulfate and administered resveratrol showed a significant reduction in MDA levels and a notable increase in serum total antioxidant capacity. Interestingly, there was a non-significant decrease in MDA levels in G2 compared to G3, suggesting that sodium thiosulfate was more effective in ameliorating the stressful effects of intraperitoneal nicotine injection than resveratrol after 28 days. Zhang et al.²⁴ reported that sodium thiosulfate is an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory agent, making it a potential therapeutic candidate targeting multiple molecular pathways. Shekari et al.²⁵ demonstrated that sodium thiosulfate had potent cardioprotective effects against doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity by suppressing oxidative stress. Additionally, resveratrol helped maintain the antioxidant defense system in rats under oxidative stress, potentially reducing renal oxidative stress.

Wang et al.²⁶ noted that pretreatment with resveratrol significantly decreased MDA levels and increased superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity. The results for red blood cell (RBC) count and hemoglobin concentration showed a marked decrease in the nicotine-stressed G1 group. In contrast, groups that received antioxidants, either sodium thiosulfate or resveratrol alone, along with nicotine, exhibited a significant increase in RBCs and Hb in rat blood. The G4 group, which received both antioxidants with nicotine, showed a significant improvement in blood parameters compared to other stressed groups, consistent with previous studies reporting a decrease in erythrocyte, hemoglobin, and hematocrit levels when exposed to nicotine. Cope et al.²⁷ indicated that smoking habits and cigarette consumption were associated

with poor blood parameter indicators, and Shukla et al.²⁸ found that smokeless tobacco users had significantly different blood profiles compared to non-users. After sodium thiosulfate treatment, G2 rats with nicotine-induced stress showed higher RBC counts and hemoglobin levels, highlighting the antioxidant and chelating properties of sodium thiosulfate.

Regarding the blood tests for G3 and G4 groups, both of which received resveratrol, improvements in RBC and Hb tests were observed. Resveratrol was suggested to cross the erythrocyte membrane, bind to hemoglobin, and alter its modulation and ATP release^{29,30}. Additionally, resveratrol activated caspase, which may play a role at high oxygenation levels of erythrocytic hemoglobin. Khudair and Al-Okaily¹³ found that resveratrol preserved antioxidant defense mechanisms in rats under oxidative stress, potentially reducing renal oxidative stress. The results for blood PO₂ values showed a significant decrease and a significant increase in blood PCO₂, along with a significant decrease in blood pH levels in animals receiving intraperitoneal nicotine injection. This pattern was consistent with previous studies indicating that changes in blood pH are primarily related to alterations in PCO₂.

Mao et al.³¹ reported that persistent prenatal nicotine exposure in rat fetuses led to decreased fetal pO₂ and increased pCO₂ and lactic acid levels, as well as reduced fetal development and hypoxia. Sodium thiosulfate was found to attenuate lung mechanics impairment and improve gas exchange, potentially through increased lung tissue glucocorticoid receptor expression. The present study revealed significant improvements in G3, G4, and G5 groups for blood PO₂, PCO₂, and blood pH, suggesting that resveratrol and sodium thiosulfate may mitigate the harmful effects of nicotine on rat blood. Resveratrol was also found to potentially reduce lung damage in rats exposed to cigarette smoke for 27 days, improving histological changes and the ratio of forced expiratory volume in 0.3 seconds to forced vital capacity.

The recent research study delves into the repercussions of intraperitoneal (I/P) nicotine injection, administered at a dosage of 1.5 mg/kg of body weight, in adult rats, with a particular focus on its influence on arterial blood pressure. The outcomes of this study shed light on a series of critical findings. First and foremost, the investigation revealed that the I/P injection of nicotine induced a notable increase in the rats' serum redox status. This suggests that nicotine exposure triggers a substantial change in the oxidative balance within the rats' circulatory system, potentially contributing to oxidative stress. However, the consequences of nicotine administration extended beyond the alteration of redox status. The study identified adverse effects on critical physiological parameters, specifically blood gases, pH levels, and the complete blood count (CBC). These findings underscore the detrimental impact of nicotine on the overall cardiovascular health of the rats, with changes in blood gases and pH levels indicating potential disruptions in acid-base balance and gas exchange within the arterial system. Intriguingly, the research also explored the potential mitigating effects of two distinct supplements: Sodium Thiocyanate (STS) and Resveratrol (RES). These supplements were administered to assess their efficacy in ameliorating the negative effects induced by nicotine exposure. The results unveiled a significant improvement in the criteria previously affected by nicotine when either STS or RES supplementation was introduced. Both STS and RES displayed a capacity to restore some semblance of normalcy to the altered parameters, suggesting their potential as interventions to counteract nicotine's adverse effects on arterial blood pressure and related physiological factors. Of particular note, the study found that STS exhibited a more pronounced and robust effectiveness as an antioxidant when compared to resveratrol. This implies that STS holds greater promise in countering the oxidative stress induced by nicotine and its repercussions on arterial blood pressure. It may, therefore, be considered a valuable avenue for further research into interventions aimed at preserving cardiovascular health in the face of nicotine exposure. In conclusion, the study underscores the detrimental impact of nicotine on arterial blood pressure and related physiological parameters in adult rats. It further highlights the potential of STS and RES as supplements to mitigate these effects, with STS emerging as a particularly promising candidate for future research into interventions for arterial blood pressure management and oxidative stress reduction.

Authors' contribution All authors checked and approved the final version of the manuscript. Competing interests There is no conflict of interest.

Ethical consideration All authors have reviewed the manuscripts for ethical concerns, such as plagiarism, permission to publish, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, multiple publishing and/or submission, and redundancy.

Conflicts of Interest: no conflict of interests.

Acknowledgments The authors would like to thank the College of Veterinary Medicine / University of Baghdad for allowing us to conduct the current research and for all of the resources and assistance they gave.

References

1. Caliri AW, Tommasi S, Besaratinia A. Relationships among smoking, oxidative stress, inflammation, macromolecular damage, and cancer. *Mutation Research/Reviews in Mutation Research*. 2021 Jan 1;787:108365.
2. Upadhyay P, Wu CW, Pham A, Zeki AA, Royer CM, Kodavanti UP, Takeuchi M, Bayram H, Pinkerton KE. Animal models and mechanisms of tobacco smoke-induced chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part B*. 2023 May 13:1-31.
3. Paulin LM, Halenar MJ, Edwards KC, Lauten K, Stanton CA, Taylor K, Hatsukami D, Hyland A, MacKenzie T, Mahoney MC, Niaura R. Association of tobacco product use with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) prevalence and incidence in Waves 1 through 5 (2013–2019) of the Population Assessment of Tobacco and Health (PATH) Study. *Respiratory research*. 2022 Dec;23(1):1-3.
4. Morjaria JB, Campagna D, Caci G, O'Leary R, Polosa R. Health impact of e-cigarettes and heated tobacco products in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: current and emerging evidence. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*. 2022 Nov 2;16(11-12):1213-26.
5. Mohammed BJ, Al-Thwani AN. Evaluation the effect of nicotine injection on the lungs of mice. *Journal of Reports in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2019 Jan 1;8(1):34.
6. Ali ZS, Khudair KK. Synthesis, characterization of silver nanoparticles using *Nigella sativa* seeds and study their effects on the serum lipid profile and DNA damage on the rats' blood treated with Hydrogen peroxide. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*. 2019;43(2):23-37.
7. Jasim Mohammed B, AL-Thwani AN, Kannan R. Demographic and genetic study for a sample of Iraqi smokers. *Cancer Biology*. 2016;6(4):16-27.
8. Nawfal AJ, Al-Okaily BN. Effect of the Sublethal Dose of Lead Acetate on Malondialdehyde, Dopamine, and Neuroglobin Concentrations in Rats. *World*. 2022 Sep 25;12(3):311-5.
9. Murad HF, Al-Okaily BN. Protective effects of alpha lipoic acid against lead-induced oxidative stress and dna fragmentation to testicular function in rats. *Biochemical & Cellular Archives*. 2020 Oct 1;20(2).
10. Merz T, Denoix N, Wepler M, Gäbler H, Messerer DA, Hartmann C, Datzmann T, Radermacher P, McCook O. H2S in acute lung injury: a therapeutic dead end (?). *Intensive Care Medicine Experimental*. 2020 Dec;8(1):1-6.

11. Khames A, Gad AM, Abd El-raouf OM, Kandeil MA, Khalaf MM. Sodium thiosulphate shows promising anti-inflammatory role against doxorubicin-induced renal injury depending on tlr4 pathway inhibition. *Plant Arch.* 2020;20(2):2948-58.
12. Ravindran S, Boovarahan SR, Shanmugam K, Vedarathinam RC, Kurian GA. Sodium thiosulfate preconditioning ameliorates ischemia/reperfusion injury in rat hearts via reduction of oxidative stress and apoptosis. *Cardiovascular drugs and therapy.* 2017 Dec;31(5-6):511-24.
13. Khudair NT, Al-Okaily BN. Renal ameliorating effect of resveratrol in hydrogen peroxide induced male rats. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences.* 2022 Jul 1;36(3):571-7.
14. Shahcheraghi SH, Salemi F, Small S, Syed S, Salari F, Alam W, Cheang WS, Saso L, Khan H. Resveratrol regulates inflammation and improves oxidative stress via Nrf2 signaling pathway: Therapeutic and biotechnological prospects. *Phytotherapy Research.* 2023 Feb 8.
15. Alghetaa H, Mohammed A, Zhou J, Singh N, Nagarkatti M, Nagarkatti P. Resveratrol-mediated attenuation of superantigen-driven acute respiratory distress syndrome is mediated by microbiota in the lungs and gut. *Pharmacological research.* 2021 May 1;167:105548.
16. Veilleux-Lemieux D, Castel A, Carrier D, Beaudry F, Vachon P. Pharmacokinetics of ketamine and xylazine in young and old Sprague-Dawley rats. *Journal of the American Association for Laboratory Animal Science.* 2013 Sep 1;52(5):567-70.
17. Baarda B, van Dijkum C. *Introduction to Statistics with SPSS.* Routledge; 2019 Nov 26.
18. Al-Shamary AN, Al-Mizraqchi AS. The Combination Effects of Honey and Nicotine on the Acid Production of Oral Mutans Streptococci.
19. Frizka Eliza F, Damayanti D, Kartika Misalina K, Septiana Widyantari S, Afif Nurul Hidayati A, Dwi Murtiastutik D. *Condylooma acuminata overlapping bacterial vaginosis under steroid therapy for SLE: A case report.* *International Journal of Health Sciences.* 2022;6(S9):179-85.
20. Raeeszadeh M, Beheshtipour J, Jamali R, Akbari A. The antioxidant properties of Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) and its biochemical, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and pathological effects on nicotine-induced oxidative stress in the rat liver. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity.* 2022 Mar 26;2022.
21. Ateyya H, Nader MA, Attia GM, El-Sherbeeny NA. Influence of alpha-lipoic acid on nicotine-induced lung and liver damage in experimental rats. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology.* 2017;95(5):492-500.
22. Malińska D, Więckowski MR, Michalska B, Drabik K, Prill M, Pataias-Krawczyk P, Walczak J, Szymański J, Mathis C, Van der Toorn M, Luettich K. Mitochondria as a possible target for nicotine action. *Journal of bioenergetics and biomembranes.* 2019 Aug 15;51:259-76.
23. Elsonbaty SM, Ismail AF. Nicotine encourages oxidative stress and impairment of rats' brain mitigated by *Spirulina platensis* lipopolysaccharides and low-dose ionizing radiation. *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics.* 2020 Aug 15;689:108382.
24. Zhang J, Li R, Man K, Yang XB. Enhancing osteogenic potential of hDPSCs by resveratrol through reducing oxidative stress via the Sirt1/Nrf2 pathway. *Pharmaceutical biology.* 2022 Dec 31;60(1):501-8.
25. Shekari M, Gortany NK, Khalilzadeh M, Abdollahi A, Ghafari H, Dehpour AR, Ghazi-Khansari M. Cardioprotective effects of sodium thiosulfate against doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity in male rats. *BMC Pharmacology and Toxicology.* 2022 May 25;23(1):32.
26. Wang XL, Li T, Li JH, Miao SY, Xiao XZ. The effects of resveratrol on inflammation and oxidative stress in a rat model of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Molecules.* 2017 Sep 12;22(9):1529.
27. Cope GF, Nayyar P, Holder R. Measurement of nicotine intake in pregnant women—associations to changes in blood cell count. *Nicotine & tobacco research.* 2001 May 1;3(2):119-22.
28. Shukla AK, Khaitan T, Gupta P, Naik SR. Smokeless tobacco and its adverse effects on hematological parameters: A cross-sectional study. *advances in preventive medicine.* 2019 Apr 1;2019.
29. Ramani R, Ramachandran A, Ravindran S, Kurian GA. Erythrocyte membrane bound ATPase and antioxidant enzyme changes associated with vascular calcification is reduced by sodium thiosulfate. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry.* 2017 Oct;32:487-92.
30. Tellone E, De Rosa MC, Pirolli D, Russo A, Giardina B, Galtieri A, Ficarra S. Molecular interactions of hemoglobin with resveratrol: potential protective antioxidant role and metabolic adaptations of the erythrocyte. *Biological Chemistry.* 2014 Mar 1;395(3):347-54.
31. Mao C, Yuan X, Zhang H, Lv J, Guan J, Miao L, Chen L, Zhang Y, Zhang L, Xu Z. The effect of prenatal nicotine on mRNA of central cholinergic markers and hematological parameters in rat fetuses. *International Journal of Developmental Neuroscience.* 2008 Aug 1;26(5):467-75.